

Evaluating UCE data adequacy and integrating uncertainty in a comprehensive phylogeny of ants

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Supplementary figures

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Concat all loci GTR by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 1: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of all 2,428 UCE loci nucleotides matrix inferred in IQ-Tree. Partitioned by locus without partition merging, GTR+F+G4 model. Likelihood score -21632150.56. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat all loci GTR PF by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 2: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of all 2,428 UCE loci nucleotides matrix inferred in IQ-Tree. Partitioned by locus with partition merging, GTR+F+G4 model. Likelihood score -21632783.89. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat all loci GTR SWSC NT

Supplementary Figure 3: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of all 2,428 UCE loci, nucleotides matrix inferred in IQ-Tree. Sliding window site characteristics, partitioned by locus with partition merging, GTR+F+G4 model. Likelihood score -21561135.66. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat all loci GTR unpart NT

Supplementary Figure 4: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of all 2,428 UCE loci, nucleotides matrix inferred in IQ-Tree. Unpartitioned, GTR+F+G4 model. Likelihood score -21843190.69. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat all loci MFP by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 5: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of all 2,428 UCE loci, nucleotides matrix inferred in IQ-Tree. Partitioned by locus without partition merging, ModelFinder choice. Likelihood score -21425962.53. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat all loci MFP PF by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 6: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of all 2,428 UCE loci, nucleotides matrix inferred in IQ-Tree. Partitioned by locus with partition merging, ModelFinder choice. Likelihood score - 21452273.97. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat all loci MFP SWSC NT

Supplementary Figure 7: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of all 2,428 UCE loci, nucleotides matrix inferred in IQ-Tree. Sliding window site characteristics, partitioned by locus with partition merging, ModelFinder choice. Likelihood score -21372031.42. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat all loci MFP unpart NT

Supplementary Figure 8: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of all 2,428 UCE loci, nucleotides matrix inferred in IQ-Tree. Unpartitioned, ModelFinder choice. Likelihood score -21622923.16. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat all loci MP NT

Supplementary Figure 9: Concatenated maximum parsimony tree of all 2,428 UCE loci, nucleotides matrix inferred in PAUP*. Unpartitioned, maximum parsimony heuristic. Values at nodes are bootstrap.

Concat all loci NJ NT

Supplementary Figure 10: Concatenated neighbor-joining tree of all 2,428 UCE loci, nucleotides matrix inferred in PAUP*. Unpartitioned, neighbor-joining uncorrected distance. Values at nodes are bootstrap.

Concat coding 3rd pos excl MFP by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 12: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 1,286 protein-coding loci nucleotides matrix with 3rd codon positions removed, inferred in IQ-Tree. Partitioned by locus with partition merging, ModelFinder choice. Likelihood score -1876166.766. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat coding 3rd pos incl MFP by codon NT

Supplementary Figure 13: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 1,286 protein-coding loci nucleotides matrix, inferred in IQ-Tree. Partitioned by locus + codon position with partition merging, ModelFinder choice. Likelihood score -12573516.53. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat coding PMSF AA

Supplementary Figure 15: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 1,286 protein-coding loci amino acids matrix, finite mixture, posterior mean site frequency inferred in IQ-Tree. Likelihood score -1447898.711. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest fail loci GTR by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 16: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix, partitioned by locus without partition merging, GTR+F+G4 model inferred in IQ-Tree. Likelihood score -12422224.6. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest fail loci GTR PF by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 17: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix, partitioned by locus with partition merging, GTR+F+G4 model inferred in IQ-Tree. Likelihood score -12421637.96. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest fail loci GTR SWSC NT

Supplementary Figure 18: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix with sliding window site characteristics, partitioned by locus with partition merging, ModelFinder choice inferred in IQ-Tree. Likelihood score -12385390.25. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest fail loci GTR unpart NT

Supplementary Figure 19: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix, unpartitioned, GTR+F+G4 model inferred in IQ-Tree. Likelihood score -12511771.63. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest fail loci MFP by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 20: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix, partitioned by locus without partition merging, ModelFinder choice inferred in IQ-Tree. Likelihood score -12308075.06. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest fail loci MFP PF by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 21: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix, partitioned by locus with partition merging, ModelFinder choice inferred in IQ-Tree. Likelihood score -12317750.44. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest fail loci MFP SWSC NT

Supplementary Figure 22: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix with sliding window site characteristics, partitioned by locus with partition merging, ModelFinder choice inferred in IQ-Tree. Likelihood score -12286977.59. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest fail loci MFP unpart NT

Supplementary Figure 23: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix, unpartitioned, ModelFinder choice inferred in IQ-Tree. Likelihood score -12385672.17. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest fail loci MP NT

Supplementary Figure 24: Concatenated maximum parsimony tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix inferred in PAUP*. Unpartitioned, inferred using maximum parsimony heuristic. Values at nodes are bootstrap.

Concat symtest fail loci NJ NT

Supplementary Figure 25: Concatenated neighbor-joining tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix inferred in PAUP*. Unpartitioned, inferred using neighbor joining uncorrected distance. Values at nodes are bootstrap.

Concat symtest pass loci GTR PF by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 27: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix, inferred in IQ-Tree. Partitioned by locus with partition merging, GTR+F+G4 model. Likelihood score -9125042.476. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest pass loci GTR SWSC NT

Supplementary Figure 28: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix with sliding window site characteristics, inferred in IQ-Tree. Partitioned by locus with partition merging, GTR+F+G4 model. Likelihood score -9142122.509. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest pass loci GTR unpart NT

Supplementary Figure 29: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix, unpartitioned, GTR+F+G4 model inferred in IQ-Tree. Likelihood score -9304822.233. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest pass loci MFP by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 30: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix, inferred in IQ-Tree. Partitioned by locus without partition merging, ModelFinder choice. Likelihood score -9112043.192. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest pass loci MFP PF by locus NT

Supplementary Figure 31: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix, inferred in IQ-Tree. Partitioned by locus with partition merging, ModelFinder choice. Likelihood score -9126535.656. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest pass loci MFP SWSC NT

Supplementary Figure 32: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix with sliding window site characteristics, inferred in IQ-Tree. Partitioned by locus with partition merging, ModelFinder choice. Likelihood score -9140956.623. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest pass loci MFP unpart NT

Supplementary Figure 33: Concatenated maximum likelihood tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix, unpartitioned, ModelFinder choice inferred in IQ-Tree. Likelihood score -9214162.033. Values at nodes are SH-aLRT / UFboot. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Concat symtest pass loci MP NT

Supplementary Figure 34: Concatenated maximum parsimony tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix inferred in PAUP*. Unpartitioned, inferred using maximum parsimony heuristic. Values at nodes are bootstrap.

Concat symtest pass loci NJ NT

Supplementary Figure 35: Concatenated neighbor-joining tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix inferred in PAUP*. Unpartitioned, inferred using neighbor joining uncorrected distance. Values at nodes are bootstrap.

SpTree ASTRAL all loci collapsed NT

Supplementary Figure 36: Coalescent tree of all 2,428 loci nucleotides matrix inferred using shortcut coalescence in ASTRAL. Values at nodes are local posterior probabilities.

SpTree ASTRAL all loci uncollapsed NT

Supplementary Figure 37: Coalescent tree of all 2,428 loci nucleotides matrix inferred using shortcut coalescence in ASTRAL. Values at nodes are local posterior probabilities.

SpTree ASTRAL symtest pass loci collapsed NT

Supplementary Figure 38: Coalescent tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix inferred using shortcut coalescence in ASTRAL. Values at nodes are local posterior probabilities.

SpTree ASTRAL symtest pass loci uncollapsed NT

Supplementary Figure 39: Coalescent tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix inferred using shortcut coalescence in ASTRAL. Values at nodes are local posterior probabilities.

SpTree ASTRAL symtest fail loci collapsed NT

Supplementary Figure 40: Coalescent tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix inferred using shortcut coalescence in ASTRAL. Values at nodes are local posterior probabilities.

SpTree ASTRAL symtest fail loci uncollapsed NT

Supplementary Figure 41: Coalescent tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix inferred using shortcut coalescence in ASTRAL. Values at nodes are local posterior probabilities.

SpTree SVDQ all loci NT

Supplementary Figure 42: Coalescent tree of all 2,428 loci nucleotides matrix inferred using singular value decomposition scores in PAUP*. Values at nodes are bootstrap.

SpTree SVDQ symtest pass loci NT

Supplementary Figure 43: Coalescent tree of 1,504 loci passing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix inferred using singular value decomposition scores in PAUP*. Values at nodes are bootstrap.

SpTree SVDQ symtest fail loci NT

Supplementary Figure 44: Coalescent tree of 924 loci failing symmetry tests, nucleotides matrix inferred using singular value decomposition scores in PAUP*. Values at nodes are bootstrap.

Concordance node numbers on consensus tree

Supplementary Figure 45: Consensus tree. Node numbers correspond to those in Supplementary Table 9.

Concordance tree node numbers

Supplementary Figure 46: Concatenated tree used for simulations. Node numbers correspond to those in Figure 3B of the manuscript and Supplementary Table 10.

Empirical tree used for simulations – UFboot / gCF / sCF

Supplementary Figure 47: Concordance factors on concatenated, unpartitioned GTR+F+G4 tree used for simulations. Values at nodes are UFboot / gCF / sCF. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Tree inferred from simulations – UFboot / gCF / sCF

Supplementary Figure 48: Concordance factors on concatenated tree inferred from simulated data. Values at nodes are UFboot / gCF / sCF. Scale bar in substitutions per site.

Supplementary Figure 49: MCMCTree chronogram inferred from 100 clock-like loci under uniform root age prior of 129 to 158 Ma and correlated clock model. Also see Supplementary Data.

Supplementary Figure 50: MCMCTree chronogram inferred from 100 clock-like loci under uniform root age prior of 129 to 158 Ma and independent clock model. Also see Supplementary Data.

Supplementary Figure 51: MCMCTree chronogram inferred from 100 clock-like loci under uniform root age prior of less than 224 Ma and correlated clock model. Also see Supplementary Data.

Supplementary Figure 52: MCMCTree chronogram inferred from 100 clock-like loci under uniform root age prior of less than 224 Ma and independent clock model. Also see Supplementary Data.